

IMPLEMENTATION AND IMPACT OF THE SPECIAL TRAINING FOR EMPLOYMENT PROGRAM (STEP) IN BARANGAY BOI, BOAC, MARINDUQUE: ADDRESSING VOCATIONAL TRAINING NEEDS AND ENHANCING EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13731959>

ABSTRACT

The Special Training for Employment Program (STEP), initiated by the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), is designed to empower marginalized communities by providing accessible, community-based vocational training. This study assesses the implementation and outcomes of STEP in Barangay Boi, Boac, Marinduque—a rural area with limited access to education and employment. Employing a descriptive research design, the study utilized participant observations, surveys, and interviews with program participants and stakeholders. Results demonstrate that STEP significantly enhanced vocational skills and improved employment opportunities among participants, leading to increases in productivity, income, and self-reliance. Nonetheless, challenges such as limited digital access and logistical difficulties were identified. Overall, the study underscores STEP's effectiveness as a vocational training model for similarly underserved regions, while also highlighting areas for improvement.

Keywords: *Special Training for Employment Program, TESDA, vocational training, rural development, employment opportunities*

INTRODUCTION

The Special Training for Employment Program (STEP), administered by the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), is a crucial initiative

aimed at addressing vocational training needs and enhancing employment opportunities in underserved regions of the Philippines. As a strategic component of TESDA's broader mission, STEP provides targeted scholarships to economically disadvantaged individuals, enabling them to access vocational training that aligns with current labor market demands (TESDA, 2020). This program is particularly significant for communities like Barangay Boi in Boac, Marinduque, where access to quality vocational education and formal employment opportunities is limited.

TESDA's approach to Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) encompasses a range of initiatives designed to improve the effectiveness and reach of vocational training programs. Key among these initiatives are skills training and certification programs, which are supported by various scholarship schemes, including STEP. These scholarships aim to reduce financial barriers and increase access to relevant training, thereby enhancing participants' employability and career prospects (TESDA, 2023). TESDA's commitment to aligning training programs with industry needs is reflected in its development of training regulations and competency standards, which ensure that the skills taught are in demand in the labor market.

In addition to direct training programs, TESDA actively promotes the value of TVET through advocacy and partnerships. The agency works with local government units, private sector companies, and international organizations to expand the reach and impact of its initiatives. These collaborations facilitate the implementation of training programs and provide additional resources and support to participants (TESDA, 2020). Furthermore, TESDA's National TVET Plan outlines strategic directions for advancing vocational education, focusing on improving quality, accessibility, and regional equity in training opportunities (TESDA, 2020).

The effectiveness of vocational education and training (VET) programs, particularly those supported by scholarships, is well-documented in the literature. The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2018) highlights the role of VET in achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by addressing skills gaps and enhancing employment outcomes. Successful examples from developed economies, such as Germany's dual education system and community colleges in the United States, demonstrate how scholarship-supported VET programs can reduce unemployment and promote job stability (Carnevale, Garcia, & Gulish, 2017; Euler, 2013). Similarly, scholarship-supported VET initiatives in Asia, such as South Korea's vocational high schools and India's "Skill India" program, showcase their impact on job readiness and economic development (FICCI, 2016; Kang, 2016).

In the Philippine context, TESDA's STEP program represents a targeted effort to improve vocational training and employment outcomes. By providing scholarships and localized training interventions, STEP aims to uplift marginalized communities, including out-of-school youth, and address specific regional challenges (TESDA, 2020). Empirical evidence from TESDA's programs indicates a positive impact on employment outcomes and income levels among graduates, underscoring the effectiveness of such initiatives in advancing national development goals (TESDA, 2018). The introduction of STEP in

Barangay Boi exemplifies this targeted approach, addressing the community's socio-economic challenges and enhancing local employment prospects. This research will explore the implementation and impact of STEP in Barangay Boi, offering valuable insights into the effectiveness of TESDA's initiatives and their role in improving vocational training and employment opportunities.

Research Questions

1. What are the vocational training needs of out-of-school youth in Barangay Boi, Boac?
2. How effectively does the STEP program address these vocational training needs?
3. To what extent does the STEP program equip participants with practical skills relevant to employment opportunities?
4. What challenges were encountered during the implementation of the STEP program?
5. What impacts has the STEP program had on participants' employment opportunities?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Barangay Boi, Boac, Marinduque, focusing on the out-of-school youth and other community members as the primary beneficiaries of the Special Training for Employment Program (STEP). The research employed a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative research methods to gather comprehensive data. A purposive sampling method was used to select participants, ensuring that those most likely to benefit from the STEP program were included.

Data Gathering Instruments

To ensure the reliability and validity of the collected data, the researchers developed and pilot-tested several instruments. First, surveys were administered to participants, incorporating both Likert scale items and open-ended questions. The Likert scale items measured satisfaction, skill acquisition, and perceived impacts of the program, while the open-ended questions provided participants the opportunity to share their thoughts and experiences in more detail. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with participants, trainers, and local officials. These interviews offered in-depth insights into the program's implementation, successes, and challenges, exploring personal experiences, training effectiveness, and any barriers encountered. Lastly, participant observation was carried out during training sessions and community interactions. This involved direct, on-site observations of the training process, participant engagement, and the dynamics between trainers and participants. Detailed field notes

were taken to document behaviors, interactions, and the overall environment, providing rich qualitative data that complemented the survey and interview findings.

Data Analysis

For data analysis, quantitative data from the surveys were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including frequency distributions, means, and standard deviations. This provided a clear overview of participants' satisfaction levels, skill acquisition, and the perceived impact of the training program. On the other hand, qualitative data from interviews and observations were analyzed through thematic analysis. This process involved coding the data to identify key themes and patterns emerging from participants' responses and observed behaviors. Thematic analysis enabled the researchers to interpret the qualitative data within the context of the study's objectives, uncovering deeper insights into the participants' experiences and the program's implementation.

Training Induction Program

The implementation of the STEP program began with a comprehensive Training Induction Program conducted by the TESDA Provincial Office. This induction was critical in orienting participants to the program's objectives, structure, and benefits. The induction sessions were strategically held in accessible locations to ensure maximum participation.

Table 1: Training Induction Program Conducted by TESDA Provincial Office

Session	Date	Venue	Number of Participants	Key Activities
1	7/23/2024	Barangay Hall, Boi	45	Overview of STEP, Introduction to Trainers
2	7/24/2024	Boi Catholic Church	45	Orientation on Training Modules, Q&A Sessions
3	7/26/2024	TESDA Office, Marinduque	45	Distribution of Training Materials, Ice-breaking Activities

The induction sessions were strategically held in accessible locations to ensure maximum participation. By choosing venues within and near Barangay Boi, the program successfully accommodated participants from remote areas, mitigating the geographical barriers to participation.

Figure 1: Location Map of Training Venues

Photo Courtesy of Google Earth

The effectiveness of the induction program was evidenced by the high levels of participation and engagement in the subsequent training sessions. The strategic implementation of the induction program ensured that participants were well-prepared, resulting in high retention and completion rates. These outcomes align with best practices in vocational training, which emphasize the importance of preparatory programs in enhancing participant readiness and program success (Carnevale, Garcia, & Gulish, 2017; Euler, 2013).

Qualitative Process

The qualitative aspect of this study was crucial in gaining a deep understanding of the participants' lived experiences and the specific contextual factors that influenced the implementation of the Special Training for Employment Program (STEP). The process began with the development of an interview protocol, where a semi-structured interview guide was carefully crafted to align with the study's objectives. The questions were designed to delve into the participants' motivations for joining the program, their experiences during the training, and the challenges they encountered.

Data collection involved conducting in-person interviews at locations convenient for the participants. Each interview was audio-recorded with the participants' consent and later transcribed verbatim for analysis. Additionally, observations were made during training sessions, with real-time notes taken and subsequently transcribed into detailed field notes.

The analysis of the data followed a thematic approach, conducted in several stages. Initially, the transcripts and observation notes were read multiple times to ensure a thorough understanding of the data. From this, initial codes were generated based on recurring topics or significant statements. These codes were then organized into broader themes that encapsulated the core experiences of the participants and the key aspects of the program's implementation. The themes were meticulously reviewed and refined to ensure they accurately represented the data and aligned with the research objectives.

To validate the findings, a triangulation process was employed, where data from surveys, interviews, and observations were compared and contrasted. This approach allowed for the identification of consistencies and discrepancies, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the program's impact and the challenges faced during its implementation.

By incorporating these qualitative processes, the study provided a nuanced analysis of the STEP program's effectiveness and the specific vocational training needs of the community in Barangay Boi. This approach ensured that the findings were deeply rooted in the participants' lived experiences, adding depth and context to the overall results.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study, analyzing the impact of the Special Training for Employment Program (STEP) on vocational training needs, program satisfaction, skill acquisition, and the program's influence on employment in Barangay Boi, Boac, Marinduque. The results are categorized into five key areas: Vocational Training Needs, Program Satisfaction, Skill Acquisition, Impact on Employment, and Challenges Encountered. Both quantitative data (survey results) and qualitative insights (open-ended responses) are discussed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the program's outcomes.

Results for Research Question 1. Vocational Training Needs

The survey conducted to identify specific vocational training needs among participants yielded the results shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Identified Vocational Training Needs by Percentage of Participants

Training Need	Percentage of Participants (%)
Sustainable Agriculture	70%
Organic Fertilizer Production	68%
Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW)	62%
Entrepreneurship	58%

Table 2 highlights that 70% of participants expressed a need for training in sustainable agriculture, while 68% identified organic fertilizer production as a priority. Additionally, 62% of participants indicated a significant demand for training in Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW), followed by 58% who expressed interest in entrepreneurship.

Results for Research Question 2. Effectiveness of the STEP Program

The effectiveness of the STEP program was assessed using a Likert scale survey, where participants rated their satisfaction with each training module. The results are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Participant Satisfaction with Training Modules

Training Module	Satisfaction Rating (Mean Score)
Organic Fertilizer Production	4.6
Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW)	4.5
Entrepreneurship	4.4

Table 3 indicates high levels of participant satisfaction across all training modules, with Organic Fertilizer Production receiving the highest mean satisfaction score of 4.6, closely followed by Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) with a mean score of 4.5.

Results for Research Question 3. Skill Acquisition

The next section of the questionnaire evaluated the skills participants acquired through the STEP program. Table 4 presents the results.

Table 4. Skill Acquisition and Application

Statement	Mean Score
I gained practical skills that I can apply in my work.	4.7
The training has increased my confidence in performing tasks.	4.6
The skills I acquired are directly relevant to employment opportunities.	4.5
I feel better prepared to seek employment after completing the STEP program.	4.4
The program equipped me with in-demand skills in the local labor market.	4.5

Table 4 demonstrates that participants perceived significant skill acquisition through the STEP program, with the highest mean score of 4.7 for the statement "I gained practical skills that I can apply in my work."

Results for Research Question 4. Impact on Employment

The impact of the STEP program on participants' employment prospects was also assessed, as summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Impact on Employment Opportunities

Statement	Mean Score
The training improved my chances of finding a job.	4.5
I have seen positive changes in my employment status.	4.4
The program opened new job opportunities for me.	4.3
I have experienced an increase in income since completing it.	4.2
I would recommend the STEP program to others.	4.7

Table 5 illustrates that participants generally experienced positive impacts on their employment status, with a mean score of 4.5 for the statement "The training improved my chances of finding a job" and a mean score of 4.7 for the statement "I would recommend the STEP program to others."

Results for Research Question 5. Challenges Encountered

Participants reported various challenges related to the program, particularly in terms of digital access and logistics. The percentage of participants facing each challenge is presented in Figure 1.

CHALLENGES FACED BY STEP PROGRAM PARTICIPANTS

Figure 2. Challenges Faced by Participants

The data in Figure 1 show that 45% of participants experienced issues with digital access, while 35% faced transportation difficulties that affected their ability to attend training sessions regularly.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reveal a strong alignment between the Special Training for Employment Program (STEP) and the specific vocational training needs of the community in Barangay Boi, Boac, Marinduque. The high demand for training in organic fertilizer production underscores the community's commitment to agricultural sustainability. This interest is likely driven by the rising costs of chemical fertilizers and a growing shift toward environmentally friendly practices, reflecting broader global trends in

sustainable agriculture (Reganold & Wachter, 2016). The qualitative feedback further supports this observation, with participants emphasizing the economic benefits of the training. For instance, one participant noted, *"The training in organic fertilizer production is vital because it helps us reduce costs and increase our farm's productivity."* This statement illustrates that the program is not only addressing immediate financial concerns but is also fostering long-term sustainability goals within the community.

Similarly, the 62% demand for Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW) training highlights the community's awareness of local employment opportunities in the construction and metalwork industries. One participant remarked, *"I want to learn welding because there are many job opportunities in our area, especially in construction and metalwork."* This indicates a direct connection between the vocational training needs and the local labor market, suggesting that the community is proactively adapting to available employment opportunities.

These findings, both quantitative and qualitative, confirm that the identified training needs are crucial for the community's economic development. The data imply that the STEP program is not only addressing current needs but is also preparing participants for sustainable livelihoods, thereby supporting the long-term economic resilience of the community.

The high levels of satisfaction reported by participants can be attributed to the program's practical, hands-on approach, which appears to have translated directly into employment opportunities. For example, a participant who rated the SMAW module highly stated, *"The welding training was very practical, and I got a job right after completing it."* This feedback underscores the effectiveness of the program in providing skills that are immediately applicable in the job market—a critical success factor for vocational training programs (Barrera-Osorio et al., 2018).

Moreover, the success of the organic fertilizer production module aligns with local agricultural practices, further enhancing its relevance. One participant shared, *"After the training, I was able to apply what I learned immediately on my farm, and I saw a significant improvement in crop yields."* This indicates that the training was not only well-received but also effective in improving participants' livelihoods, contributing to both food security and sustainable agriculture within the community.

These qualitative responses complement the quantitative data, offering a holistic understanding of the program's effectiveness. The evidence suggests that the STEP program successfully met participants' vocational training needs, leading to tangible improvements in their skills, employment opportunities, and overall economic well-being.

The overwhelmingly positive feedback regarding the practical skills gained through the program is reflected in the high mean score of 4.7 for skill acquisition. This aligns with qualitative comments from participants, such as, *"The skills I learned in this program are exactly what employers in our area are looking for."* This suggests that the STEP program not only met but exceeded expectations in preparing participants for the local job market.

The high ratings for skill acquisition are consistent with previous research, which shows that vocational training programs emphasizing practical skills and alignment with local labor market demands tend to lead to better employment outcomes (Carnevale et al., 2017). Participants' reports of increased confidence and preparedness resonate with studies of technical education in the Asia-Pacific region, where skill-based learning has been shown to enhance job readiness (UNESCO, 2019).

The results also indicate that the STEP program had a positive impact on employment opportunities for the majority of participants, with many reporting improvements in job prospects and income. One participant shared, *"After completing the program, I was able to find a better-paying job, which has significantly improved my family's livelihood."* This finding is in line with studies highlighting the role of vocational training in improving job prospects, particularly in rural and underserved communities. For instance, the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2018) found that targeted vocational training programs significantly enhance employability in such contexts. The reported increase in income aligns with Kluve et al.'s (2017) findings, which demonstrate that vocational training can lead to higher earnings and better job stability.

Furthermore, the high recommendation rates for the STEP program (mean score of 4.7) mirror evaluations of similar programs by the World Bank (2019), which noted that participants in successful vocational training programs are more likely to recommend them due to perceived benefits in employment and income generation.

However, the study also identified significant challenges, particularly related to digital access and logistics, which reflect broader systemic issues in rural areas. The challenge of unreliable internet connectivity, reported by 45% of participants, is a significant barrier to fully engaging with the program. One participant commented, *"The lack of reliable internet in our area made it difficult to access some of the training materials online."* This issue is particularly relevant given the increasing reliance on digital platforms for education and training, a trend exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic (UNESCO, 2020).

Transportation difficulties, reported by 35% of participants, further underscore the logistical challenges faced by rural communities. For example, one participant noted, *"It was hard to attend every session because of transportation problems, especially during the rainy season."* This reflects the broader infrastructural challenges in rural areas, where poor road conditions and limited public transport options can significantly hinder access to education and training programs.

These challenges suggest that while the STEP program was effective in its content delivery, its accessibility was compromised by external factors. Addressing these barriers will be crucial for future iterations of the program to ensure that all participants can fully benefit from the training.

Integration of Findings

The integration of quantitative and qualitative data provides a comprehensive picture of the STEP program's impact. The program was highly effective in addressing the vocational training needs of participants, as evidenced by high satisfaction ratings, practical skill acquisition, and positive impacts on employment. However, challenges related to digital access and transportation remain significant barriers that must be addressed to ensure the program's full effectiveness in rural settings.

Conclusions

The STEP program in Barangay Boi, Boac, Marinduque, successfully met the vocational training needs of the community, leading to improved employment opportunities and economic outcomes for participants. However, the challenges highlighted in this study, particularly those related to digital access and transportation, underscore the need for more context-specific solutions in rural training programs (Carnevale et al., 2017; Kluve et al., 2017). Future programs should incorporate strategies to mitigate these barriers, ensuring equitable access to vocational training for all participants.

Recommendations

1. **Expansion of Training Modules:** Additional training modules focusing on other high-demand skills in the region, such as eco-tourism and fishery management, should be considered.
2. **Enhancement of Digital Infrastructure:** Collaborating with local government units and telecom providers to improve digital access in rural areas is crucial for the program's long-term success.
3. **Flexible Training Delivery:** The introduction of mobile training units or community-based training hubs could address logistical challenges and improve accessibility for participants from remote areas.
4. **Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** Implementing a robust monitoring and evaluation framework will help track the program's long-term impact and identify areas for improvement.

By addressing these recommendations, the STEP program can continue to serve as a model for effective vocational training in rural communities, contributing to the broader goals of sustainable development and inclusive economic growth.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The undersigned is conducting research entitled "Implementation and Impact of the Special Training for Employment Program (STEP) in Barangay Boi, Boac, Marinduque: Addressing Vocational Training Needs and Enhancing Employment Opportunities." This study investigates the implementation and impact of the STEP

program to address vocational training needs and improve employment opportunities in Barangay Boi.

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and participants have the right to withdraw at any time without facing any consequences. The information collected will be used solely for research purposes and will be treated with the highest level of confidentiality. All data will be handled securely, and personal identifiers will be removed to protect participant privacy.

For any questions or concerns regarding the research or the data collection process, please do not hesitate to contact the researcher at lautzojam@gmail.com or 09687191434. Your participation is greatly valued, and your insights are vital for enhancing vocational training and employment opportunities in the community.

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our deepest gratitude to all those who contributed to the successful completion of this research study on the Special Training for Employment Program (STEP) in Barangay Boi, Boac, Marinduque.

First and foremost, we extend our sincere appreciation to the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) for their unwavering support and commitment to improving vocational training in underserved communities. Special thanks to the TESDA Provincial Office for facilitating the Training Induction Program and providing valuable resources and guidance throughout the study.

We are profoundly grateful to the participants of the STEP program, including the out-of-school youth and community members of Barangay Boi, for their willingness to share their experiences and insights. Their honest feedback and active participation were instrumental in assessing the program's impact and effectiveness.

Our heartfelt thanks also go to the local officials, trainers, and community leaders who assisted in the implementation and evaluation of the STEP program. Their cooperation and support were crucial in overcoming the challenges faced during the study.

We would like to acknowledge the contributions of our research team members, who dedicated their time and expertise to conducting surveys, interviews, and observations. Their hard work and dedication were key to the success of this research.

Additionally, we appreciate the guidance and feedback from our peers and colleagues, whose constructive critiques and suggestions helped refine the study and enhance its overall quality.

Finally, we wish to thank our families for their understanding and encouragement throughout the research process. Their support provided us with the strength and motivation to complete this study.

This research was made possible through the collective efforts of everyone involved, and we are grateful for their contributions to addressing the vocational training needs and enhancing employment opportunities in Barangay Boi.

Thank you all for your invaluable support.

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